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Uncovering Neural Saccadic Responses using EEG during Natural Viewing of Paintings

Iffah Syafiqah binti Suhaili and Zoltan Juhasz

Laboratory of Bioelectric Brain Imaging
Department of Electrical Engineering and Information Systems
University of Pannonia, Veszprem, Hungary

ssiffah@phd.uni-pannon.hu, juhasz@virt.uni-pannon.hu

Extended Abstract

Introduction

EEG is the most frequently used tool in cognitive research due to its low cost, non-invasive measurement approach and high temporal resolution. Due to the low signal-to-noise ratio of EEG, the traditional approach is to average multiple trials (stimulus related response) together to measure brain activity in a given cognitive task. This method, the Event-Related Potential or ERP, can only be used in strictly controlled experiments where response to stimulus is fast, and phase and time-locked, and head and eye movements are minimised.

Unfortunately, everyday activities require natural viewing conditions that include body and eye movements, evoke responses to different visual stimuli, and the duration can span seconds or minutes. Under these conditions, the ERP technique is not usable. In addition, the uncontrolled conditions increase the occurrence of unwanted artifacts (eye blinks and movements, muscle noise) that greatly distort the registered EEG signal. These severely limit the ability to research the execution of complex cognitive tasks. As an alternative, eye-tracking devices are used that can register eye fixation, saccades, and microsaccades but lack the information of brain activity.

In this paper, we explore the possibility to extract saccadic neural responses from EEG recordings only, without eye-tracking device and artefact distortions. We show that the Independent Component Analysis (ICA) based artefact removal method can be used to identify perception related activations in a natural environment such as free viewing art paintings.

Methods

We created an experiment in which participants view a series of painting, as shown in Fig. 1. Each painting is displayed on the screen for 8 seconds

followed by 4 seconds for a key-press response (“like” or “dislike”) and a 1-second number cue. Brain activity is registered on the scalp of the participants with a 128-channel Biosemi ActiveTwo EEG measurement instrument with 2048 Hz sampling rate.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the EEG experiment for visual art perception.

After the typical pre-processing steps (high-pass filtering at 1 Hz, low-pass filtering at 40 Hz and down-sampling the signal to 512 Hz sampling rate) we performed Independent Component Analysis [1] to separate neural and non-neural (artifact) activity sources into independent components, ICs.

Results and discussion

Fig. 2 shows a subset (IC1-9) of the independent components obtained from ICA over the duration of two painting view epochs. Vertical green lines mark the appearance of the painting, whereas vertical pink lines indicate participant response execution. Horizontal axis denotes time in seconds. IC1 and IC 3 represent vertical and horizontal eye movements, respectively. IC2, 4 and 5 show neural activity with increased alpha oscillations after the responses. IC6 shows a unique pattern of “spike train” during the painting displayed. One epoch of IC6 is shown in the bottom of the figure with peaks highlighted. On the right, the spatial map of IC6 is shown, clearly marking an occipital activation area.

Previous research identified the role of microsaccades in perception [2] and their presence as artifacts in EEG along with saccade-induced lambda waves. Methods using eye-tracking combined with ERP analysis have been successful in monitoring visual attention during free-viewing tasks [3], [4]. No research is known to us that used ICA to identify these spikes. Our analysis suggests a potential connection between these spikes and lambda waves, saccades, and microsaccades. The ICA approach can allow us to detect tiny eye movements and also—implicitly—attention, or to remove unwanted occipital activation from natural viewing experiments that would otherwise overshadow underlying neural activity. It is important to highlight

that this research is in an exploratory stage, and we are continuing to explore this topic in the future to gain a more comprehensive understanding.

Figure 2. Independent components of two painting view epochs (top), with zoomed in occipital lambda response component (bottom) and activation map (right).

Conclusions

This study suggested that EEG can be used with Independent Component Analysis for studying neural saccadic response phenomena as a standalone method during free-viewing tasks. The method can open up new opportunities for cognitive research in studying visual perception, attention, and activation sequences in the human brain.

References

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